

ON THE ETHNIC AFFINITY BETWEEN THE JAPANESE AND UZBEKS ЯПОНЛАР ВА ЎКУЗБЕКЛАРДАГИ ЭТНИК ЯҚИНЛИК ҲАҚИДА

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15569730>

Urak LAFASOV,

Candidate of Philological Sciences

Associate Professor of the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies,

lafas1963@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0002-0557-3476

Аннотация: Ушбу (“Японлар ва ўқузбеклардаги этник яқинлик ҳақида”) мақолада Нуҳ пайгамбарнинг фарзанди бўлган Ёфасга отаси берган ҳудудлар, бу жойларнинг Турон эканлиги, турлар, Туроннинг шарқий чегарасидаги Жобарқо акс этган харита ҳақида маълумот берилган. Туроннинг маркази бўлган Ўқузия, турларнинг аслзодаси бўлган ўқузбеклар, айн//айнлилар қўнрот ва қўтжи ўзбеклари таркибидаги эл эканлиги, айнлар Ўрта Осиёдан Туроннинг шарқидаги чегара ҳудудга кўчганлиги, уларнинг бир қисми Жанубий Сибирда, Камчатка, Сахалин, Курил оролларида қолганлиги, туркий тилда “кур” (қўрқмас) маъносини англатиши шарҳланган. Айнларнинг иккинчи қисми Жобарқо (қуруқлик бор жой) боришганлиги, уларнинг миллий байроғи, бексакларга яқинлиги, туркий тилда “айн” (ақли) маъносини билдириши, айнларнинг умумий сони, айнларнинг тарихи, илк япон давлати, японча “тэнно” терминининг туркий “тегин”, “тегит” атамаларига, “сёгун” терминининг туркий “сагун” атамасига, японча “самурай” терминининг туркий “сангун” атамасига алоқадорлиги изоҳланган. Мунгул(аслзода) ларнинг денгиз тўфони сабабли Японияни забт эта олмаганлари, Япония тарихидаги сёгунлари сулоласи, “Мейдзи исин” исёни ва Хоккайдо, Хонсю топонимлари тўғрисида қайдлар берилган. “Хон” туркий термин эканлиги, японларнинг ўқузияликлар билан қадимий савдо алоқалари, Япониядаги айнлар музейи, сайргоҳи, айнларнинг Япониянинг туб аҳолиси сифатида расмий тан олинishi, япон тилининг Олтой тиллар оиласига мансублиги, япон тилига кирган ўзлашмалар ва япон ёзуви каби масалалар ёритилган.

Таянч иборалар: Нуҳ пайгамбар, Ёфас, Турон, турлар, ўқузбеклар, айнлар, курлар, Курил ороллари, Жобарқо.

Abstract: This article provides information about the territories that Noah's father gave to his son Japheth, the fact that these places are in Turon, the tribes, and the map reflecting Jobarqo, which is located on the eastern border of Turon. It discusses Okuzia, the center of Turon, the Uzbeks, who are the descendants of the Tur, and the Ain (Ainli) people, who belong to the Kongrot and Qutji Uzbek tribes. It is explained that the Ain people migrated from Central Asia to the eastern border of Turon, with some of them remaining in Southern Siberia, Kamchatka, Sakhalin, and the Kuril Islands. The Turkish word “kur” meaning “fearless” is also mentioned. The article also discusses the second part of the Ain people moving to Jobarqo (a place with dry land), their national flag, their closeness to the Beksaks, the meaning of “ain” in Turkish (wise), the total number of Ain people, their history, the first Japanese state, and the connection of the Japanese

term “tenno” with the Turkish terms “tegin” and “tegit.” It further explores the relationship of the Japanese term “shogun” with the Turkish term “sagun,” and the connection between the Japanese term “samurai” and the Turkish word “sangun.” The article discusses the inability of the Mongols (noble ancestors) to conquer Japan due to a sea storm, the shogunate families in Japanese history, the “Meiji Restoration” rebellion, and the toponyms of Hokkaido and Honshu. It notes that “Hon” is a Turkish term, mentions the ancient trade relations between the Japanese and the Okuzia people, and describes the Ain people’s museum and park in Japan. It also highlights the official recognition of the Ain people as the indigenous population of Japan, the affiliation of the Japanese language with the Altai language family, the integration of loanwords into the Japanese language, and issues related to the Japanese writing system.

Key words: Noah’s prophet, Japheth, Turon, tribes, Uzbeks, Ains, Kur people, Kuril Islands, Jobarqo.

Introduction

There is specific information about the territories given to Japheth, the son of Noah (peace be upon him), by his father in the works of Mahmud Kashgari’s “*Devonu lugat-ib turk*,” Mirzo Ulughbek’s “*The History of the Four Uluses*,” and Abulghazi Bahadur Khan’s “*Shajare-i Turk*”.

Since Japheth ibn Noah’s second name was **Tur**, the land allocated to him was called Turon, and the descendants of his nine sons were called **Tur**. Noah, peace be upon him, “had designated Turon and Turkestan for Japheth, peace be upon him.” For this reason, he was given the title “*Abu-t-Turk*” (Father of the Turks).

The name of the islands where modern-day Japan is located, which was considered the eastern border of Great Turon, was originally **Jobarqo**. This information is mentioned in Mahmud Kashgari’s “*Devonu lugat-ib turk*” and the region is clearly marked on the map [1].

The area between the Okuz and Inju Okuz rivers, which was the center of Turon, was called Okuzia. In Okuzia, the descendants of the Tur, the Uzbeks (*Kudji, Qiyot, Kongrot, and Naiman*), lived [2].

The Ainli/Aynli/Ayilli people are part of the Kongrot and Qutji Uzbeks. They are divided into two main clans, and each clan is further divided into tribes: 1) *Aqtonli, Beshbola, Oytamgali, Oqtana, Turkman, Churan, and others*; 2) *Qoratonli, Qoraqalpoq, Quvuq, Qochay, Tunsar, Yomgurchi, and similar tribes* [3].

In ancient times, the Ain people, who were part of the **Qutji** and **Kongrot tribes**, migrated from Central Asia towards the eastern border of Turon. Some of them remained in Southern Siberia, as well as in Sakhalin, in Kamchatka and the Kuril Islands [4].

The Kurians living in the present day Kuril Islands, South and North Kuria//Korea are also a people formed from the fusion of Ain and Tungus. They moved in a north-easterly direction and settled north-east of Turon.

In 18th-century Russian sources about the Kurds, the Turkic word “kür” (in the ethnonym “kur+il+lar” – *kurily*) was incorrectly interpreted as “*fearless*” [1].

314] or “cunning” [5]. Russian scholars have described the Kurds, who belong to an Asiatic race, as Europeans.

The second part of the Ain, who moved to the southeast, sailed from the sea in boats to land and came to *Jobarqo*. The meaning of this toponym: جَابِرْقا [1.65] جا ja [7] – *place*, بَر bar [1. 341] – *there is*, قَى qa(q) [1. 386] – **dryness**) that is, “the place where there is land”.

The fact that the Ains belong to the Turlar tribe is also confirmed by their national flag. It is recognized by world scholars that the Scythians/Huns used bows and arrows and round shields to lay the foundations of two of the world’s earliest civilizations (Maya and Sumer).

In fact, in 19th-20th century Russian sources about the Ains, the ethnonym “ain” was incorrectly interpreted as “intelligent” or “true human.” This misinterpretation is rooted in the Uzbek proverb “*The crow knows the language of the raven,*” which indicates a misunderstanding. The Russians, unfamiliar with ethnic layers, made incorrect conclusions.

According to 2010, there are 25,000 official and 200,000 unofficial Ainu people in Japan, 109,000 people on the Kuril Islands, and 94,000 people in Kamchatka [6]. This does not include the Ainu in Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, North and South Korea.

In the second millennium BC, before the birth of Christ, a tribe led by the Mungul (noble) clan migrated from Okuzia to Jobarqa. On the eve of the first millennium BC, the main population of Jobarqa consisted of ethnic Ains.

In the 4th century AD, the first Japanese state, called Yamato, was formed by a union of large tribes, namely the Ainu and the Kuru. The capital was the city of *Nara*. *Yamato* is the name of an ancient province, plain, and river in the present-day Nara Prefecture of Japan.

In foreign relations, the title “*tenno*” began to be used for the rulers of this state. This title has been preserved to this day, and its Russian translation is “heavenly ruler” [8], which corresponds to the European term “*emperor*.”

The Japanese term “*tenno*” is derived from the Turkic word *tegin* [1. 391], meaning “a servant beloved by Allah.” The plural form of *tegin* is *tegit* [1. 337], which means “servants beloved by Allah.” After the courage shown by the Japanese ruler in battle against Alexander the Great, this title was granted to the sons of the khan.

In Japan, the northeastern people declared Minamoto Yoritomo as the state ruler in 1192 with the title of *shogun* (military commander). The capital was located in the city of Kamakura. The Japanese term *shogun* is a phonetic variation of the Turkic word *sağun*[1. 382] (leader) , Volume 1, p. 382].

The shoguns were made up of the warrior class (*bushi*, i.e., *samurai*). The Turkic word *sangun* (*sang*[9] (*sanch*) + *un* (*uvchi*)) is a phonetic variation of the term used to refer to *samurai* military nobles.

The Mongols (noble ancestors), who had conquered China and Korea, sent their military fleets in 1274 and 1281 to invade Japan. However, due to a powerful sea storm (“*kamikaze*” – “*divine wind*”), they were unable to achieve their goals.

In 1603, Ieyasu Tokugawa (1542-1616) declared himself shogun and moved the capital to Edo (*Tokyo*). The Tokugawa shogunate ruled the country justly until 1867.

During the Tokugawa shogunate, Japan became a centralized monarchy. The government maintained a legal system of four social classes (*samurai*, *peasants*, *artisans*, and *merchants*). Thanks to the peace, many achievements were made in various fields.

From the 16th century, Europeans began to arrive in Japan. In 1867-68, the “*Meiji Restoration*” rebellion occurred. The shogunate government was

overthrown, and power was handed to Emperor *Mytsyximo* (1867-1912). A three-class system (nobles, samurai, and common people) was established in the country.

Japan is an island nation. Its largest islands are *Hokkaido*, *Honshu*, *Shikoku*, and *Kyushu* [10]. Hokkaido Island is located in the northern part of Japan and ranks second in size (after Honshu/Hondo). Some of the peaks in its mountain ranges exceed 2,000 meters in height.

The toponym “Hokkaido,” the name of the island in modern Japan, was officially explained in 1968 as a combination of the Japanese words “*hoku*” – “*north*”, “*kai*” – “*sea*”, and “*do*” – “*province*”, meaning “*province in the northern sea*” [11].

In Japan, 99% of the population consists of Japanese people. The Ainu, the indigenous people of the country, also live on Hokkaido Island. Additionally, there are Koreans, Chinese, and other ethnic groups living on the Japanese islands. The official language of the state is Japanese.

The word “*hon*” in the toponym “*Honshu*” (the name of the main island of Japan) is also related to the Ainu people and means ‘leader.’ The words “*shu*” and “*do*” mean “*place*” or “*province*”.

“*Khan*” is the title of the highest leaders among the Turks. The children of *Alper Tunga* (*Afrosiyob*) were also referred to as “*khan*”, while *Alper Tunga* himself is considered a “*khagan*” (the supreme ruler) [1. 172]. “*Khon*” is an ancient word related to the Tur tribes, which has undergone changes in form, evolving from “*qon*” to “*qoon*” to “*khókon*” and “*finally*” to “*khon*”. In the Tur tribes, a *khan* was a ruler who governed a five-*khan* system.

The Japanese have had mutual trade relations with the Okuzia people since ancient times. A clear proof of this is the artifacts from Samarkand and Tashkent found in the Horuji temple in Nara, Japan, the first capital of Japan, dating back to the 8th century. Additionally, musical instruments from the 19th-20th centuries also serve as evidence of these long-standing trade connections [12].

The discovery of a fine *Japanese porcelain vessel* from the 12th century during the excavation of the *Alper Tunga* mound in ancient Semizkent (Samarkand) confirms that trade relations between the Uzbek and Ainu peoples were well-established in the past [13].

On April 2, 1984, the “*Ainu Museum*” was established in the Sirao settlement, which is home to the indigenous Ainu people. The museum was closed on March 31, 2018, due to the need for space to open the “*National Museum of the Ainu People*”. The museum was reopened on July 12, 2020, in connection with the Summer Olympic Games and the Summer Paralympic Games.

Next to the museum, there is the Ainu People’s *National Park*, which serves as a place dedicated to protecting and promoting the culture and language of the Ainu people. The Ainu participated in the opening ceremony of the XXXII Summer Olympic Games in Japan.

In 2019, the Japanese government passed a law that strengthened the human rights of the Ainu people. It was officially recognized that the Ainu are the

indigenous people of Japan. The law also granted the government permission to uphold all traditional practices related to the Ain people's way of life.

On April 19, 2019, the Japanese government passed the “Law on Measures to Build a Society that Respects the Human Dignity of the Ainu People.” It was officially acknowledged that the Ains of Hokkaido Island are the indigenous people of Japan.

Research written in the 20th century confirmed the scientific views about the Japanese language belonging to the Altai language family. In this language, the length of vowels and the sequential and paired nature of consonants serve to distinguish meanings.

It is known that in Altai languages, the defining word typically comes before the defined one. Word combinations form in the structure of noun and noun, or noun and verb. The subject of a sentence typically comes at the beginning, and the predicate comes at the end. These rules are followed in the original Japanese words.

In the Japanese language lexicon, in addition to the original Japanese words, many words borrowed from Chinese, known as “kanji” words, have entered the language along with Chinese characters. Additionally, modern borrowings from English, known as “*gairaigo*” are increasingly entering the Japanese language [14].

According to the official spelling rules in Japan, texts composed of original Japanese words, phrases, and grammatical markers are written in the “*hiragana*” form of the Japanese script. Words and phrases borrowed from foreign languages, as well as idioms, are written in the “*katakana*” form [14].

In conclusion, it can be said that the Ains, who are originally from the Tur tribes, are the indigenous people of Japan. Their language, clothing culture, appearance, and flag confirm their ethnic closeness to the noble Uzbeks.

References

1. Mahmud Koshgari. A dictionary of Turkish. Three roofs. I roof. Tashkent: “Fan”. 1960. – 499 p.
2. Lafasov U.P. Okuzbeks, their language, place in society and culture. I imagine. Number: Uzbekistan Special Number. September 2024. – 295 p.
3. Jalilov O. Important documents on the history of Karakalpak in the early 19th-20th centuries, Tashkent: – 1977 (source: UzME, vol. 1, p. 164).
4. The Great Soviet Encyclopedia (3rd ed.), in 30 volumes. Volume 1. Moscow: “Soviet Encyclopedia” 1969. – 709 p.
5. Mülller F.W.K. Uygurica II. APAN, 1910, Abb, III. pp. 77/26.
6. Russian-Persian dictionary. Moscow. Publishing house “Soviet encyclopedia”. 1965. – 1091 p.
7. Mahmud Koshgari. A dictionary of Turkish. Three roofs. Volume II. Tashkent: “Fan”. 1960. – 427 p.
8. Belyaeva Nastyia. The Main Islands of the Kuril Archipelago. Travel Journal. 09.04.2024.

9. The Great Soviet Encyclopedia (3rd ed.), in 30 volumes. 26 volumes. Moscow: “Soviet Encyclopedia”. 1977. – 725 p.
10. Drevnetyurksky dictionary (Editors D.M. Nasilova, I.V. Kormushina, A.V. Dybo, U.K. Isabekovoy). Astana: “Gylym” publishing house, 2016. – 760 p.
11. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 12. Volume 10. 2005. – 656 p.
12. Mahmud Koshgari. A dictionary of Turkish. Three roofs. Volume III. Tashkent: “Fan”. 1960. – 461 p.

